

***Collaborative Innovation in
Healthcare: the power of
Living Labs in advancing
healthcare research and
innovation***

**Panel Report - OpenLivingLab Days
Conference 2024**

Moderator

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Speakers

Panagiotis Bamidis, Professor, AUTH Lab of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Director, ThessAHALL Founder, ENoLL Health & Wellbeing WG leader

Eva Kehayia, Associate Professor, School of Physical & Occupational Therapy, McGill University

Vicky Van der Auwera, Research manager and co-founder of LiCaLab, Thomas More University of Applied Sciences

Lacramioara Stoicu-Tivadar, Professor, University Politehnica Timisoara

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Introduction

The "Collaborative Innovation in Healthcare" session at the Open Living Labs Day (OLLD) convened experts to discuss how Living Labs can transform clinical research and healthcare practices. Living Labs are collaborative ecosystems that bring together academia, industry, government, and civil society to tackle healthcare innovation challenges. The session provided a platform to explore Living Labs' potential to address cultural and systemic barriers, enhance collaboration, and make impactful contributions to healthcare innovation.

Panel Discussion Highlights

The panelists began by acknowledging the rapid evolution of healthcare, particularly through breakthroughs in areas like cancer treatment. They highlighted how Living Labs serve as ideal environments for developing, testing, and standardizing healthcare innovations, making them practical for real-world application. As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to advance, panelists discussed how Living Labs are instrumental in integrating AI-driven solutions in healthcare, enabling improved data sharing, benchmarking, and patient care.

A recurring theme in the discussion was AI's potential to empower individuals to manage their health data proactively. By facilitating citizen-driven data management and open data initiatives, Living Labs can encourage patients to take ownership of their information and engage in preventive care. This vision hints at a future where patients actively shape their healthcare experiences rather than being passive recipients of care.

Main Outcomes

Despite the potential, integrating Living Labs into existing healthcare systems presents challenges, primarily due to cultural resistance within traditional healthcare environments. Addressing this issue, Ir. Van der Auwera emphasized the need to engage professionals across all organizational levels to foster acceptance and build trust. By showcasing quick, impactful demonstrations of the benefits Living Labs bring, organizations can ease resistance to innovation. Strategic partnerships further reinforce this integration by helping healthcare teams see the immediate, tangible benefits of adopting the Living Lab model.

To align the adaptable structure of Living Labs with the more rigid frameworks of healthcare institutions, Prof. Eva Kehayia shared her experience from Canada where aligning Living Labs with healthcare often involves creating incentives, such as salary awards for healthcare professionals who participate in research and innovation. Additionally, implementing a common language and standardized practices across departments supports healthcare professionals in integrating Living Lab methods into their clinical routine. Complementing this approach, Prof. Lacramioara Stoicu-Tivadar highlighted the

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importance of involving key influencers within healthcare organizations who can champion Living Labs and inspire greater collaboration.

As the discussion progressed, the panelists identified key factors critical to the success of Living Labs. Prof. Panos Bamidis advocated for agile, patient-centered design, stressing that solutions should place patient needs at the forefront. Engaging academia, industry, government, and civil society in co-creation is essential for developing practical, real-world solutions. Prof. Kehayia further noted that creating value early in the project can foster interest and trust in Living Labs, showing healthcare professionals the advantages of collaboration and innovation. Likewise, Prof. Stoicu-Tivadar emphasized the need for assembling diverse, multidisciplinary teams to foster a collaborative culture, helping ground Living Labs in both technical expertise and varied perspectives.

Moreover, the panelists shared real-world examples where Living Labs have successfully driven systemic change in healthcare. Prof. Bamidis presented the Lifechamps project, illustrating how Living Labs can facilitate meaningful improvements in healthcare delivery and patient support. Additionally, Ir. Van der Auwera shared insights from a CrossCare program, where AI was implemented in a nursing home to train and support staff members in the daily incontinence care through a Living Lab approach, thus significantly improving care quality and outcomes. These examples reinforced the panel's message on the tangible and positive impact of Living Labs on healthcare systems.

Turning to emerging technologies, the panelists discussed how AI is opening new avenues for Living Labs in healthcare. Prof. Bamidis highlighted AI's potential to ensure healthcare innovations are standardized and practical, as unstandardized tools often fail in clinical settings. Prof. Stoicu-Tivadar supported this point with an example from the HOSMARTAI Project, showing how AI improves data sharing and benchmarking, allowing healthcare professionals to make informed patient-centered decisions. Additionally, Ir. Van der Auwera proposed that AI-driven citizen data management could empower individuals to make proactive health decisions, fostering a preventive approach to healthcare. Living Labs, in this regard, offer a foundation for this forward-thinking model, enabling patients to shape their own healthcare experiences.

Conclusion

The session closed with a shared vision that sees patients as agents of change. By involving them directly, Living Labs can drive meaningful shifts in healthcare, influencing policy and creating a more inclusive, responsive healthcare landscape. Panelists agreed that engaging healthcare professionals at every level and building partnerships across sectors are essential to ensuring that Living Labs make a lasting and positive impact on healthcare systems.